

The need for open, transdisciplinary, and ethical science in seismology

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1 Introduction

The devastating 2023 M7.8 Türkiye–Syria earthquake sequence once again highlighted the gap between (seismological) knowledge and action: Although the impacted region is known to be at high seismic risk (i.e., highly seismically active and densely populated), the political and societal conditions have complicated and delayed protective measures. To reduce the seismic risk and prepare local communities, experts from different disciplines must collaborate effectively in redesigning the built environment and engaging the community in risk education and management (Comfort et al., 2023).

In recent years, three subjects have become increasingly relevant to build that needed bridge between scientific knowledge and societal action: open science, transdisciplinarity, and ethics (see Figure 1). They have influenced scientific discussions on how to transition from purely scientific research to practical and societally relevant applications that increase societies’ resilience to disasters (e.g., Marti et al., 2022) – just as envisioned by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 project ‘Real-time earthquake rIsk reduction for a reSilient Europe’ ([RISE](#)) concerning earthquake risk.

We and other early career scientists of RISE identified these three subjects in several virtual discussions while reflecting on our needs to better understand how we can make our research efforts more societally meaningful and effective. Eventually, together with several senior scientists of RISE, we discussed and evaluated these subjects during a three-day workshop under the theme “Bringing

44 research to practical applications that increase society’s earthquake resilience” (Supplement 1). This
 45 theme resembled RISE’s overall goal to advance the scientific and societal knowledge on *dynamic*
 46 *seismic risk*, the overarching topic we additionally wanted to explore. First, keynotes from experts gave
 47 us a background on the three subjects, and lightning talks by all participants revealed the range of our
 48 expertise. Second, we drew a *rich picture* for the overarching topic and each subject following the *Soft*
 49 *Systems Methodology* (Pohl, 2020): separate groups sketch and express their ideas as mental models,
 50 receive feedback from the other groups, and revise it accordingly (see Supplement S2a-d for the
 51 evolution of the rich pictures). This approach allowed us to integrate all our expertise on the topic and
 52 subjects.

53 In the following, we provide the conceptual background of the three main subjects, stress their
 54 relevance in current research, and illustrate their link to dynamic seismic risk (Figure 1). We believe
 55 that these reflections can be transferred to any other research field since the subjects affect various
 56 disciplines.

57
 58 **Figure 1: Overview of the three subjects (open science, ethics, and transdisciplinarity) and their relevance in dynamic**
 59 **seismic risk to co-design user-centered services and products.** Ethics not only influence dynamic seismic risk, but also open
 60 science and transdisciplinarity; for example, before granting public access to scientific data or products that will be integrated
 61 in the dynamic seismic risk framework, the responsibility for consequences of any misuse must be clarified beforehand. The
 62 two empty dashed boxes at the bottom indicate further important subjects that were not addressed but are similarly relevant
 63 (e.g., legality, equality, diversity, inclusivity; Klinkhamer, 2022).

64 2 The three subjects in the light of dynamic seismic risk

65 To assess the impact of earthquakes on the built environment and people’s well-being, seismic risk
 66 combines the knowledge about the potential ground shaking due to future earthquakes (seismic hazard)
 67 with the knowledge about the exposure and vulnerability of buildings and infrastructure. Since seismic
 68 risk is not constant but dynamic (it varies in time, space, and context), different approaches must address
 69 the various challenges in different phases of the disaster cycle (i.e., before, during, and after an
 70 earthquake sequence) such as operational earthquake forecasting (Jordan et al., 2011), earthquake early
 71 warning (Allen & Melgar, 2019; Cremen & Galasso, 2020), rapid loss assessment (Erdik et al., 2014),
 72 and recovery and rebuilding efforts (Miles & Chang, 2006); see also Supplement S2a.

73 The data, models, products, and services (hereafter referred to as assets) that have been produced
74 in RISE contribute to all phases of the disaster cycle (Carr, 1932) and, taken together, address dynamic
75 seismic risk by managing the entire disaster cycle (Alexander, 2018). As outlined in the following three
76 sections, these assets can only be combined meaningfully if the inputs and outputs are openly shared
77 and documented, (societal) stakeholders are actively involved, and ethical issues are appropriately
78 considered. For every subject, we dedicate three paragraphs: (§1) the theoretical concepts and
79 advantages, (§2) their specific relevance for dynamic seismic risk, and (§3) solutions and good practices
80 to implement them in future research.

81 **2.1 Open science**

82 Open science envisions transparent and accessible knowledge that is shared and developed
83 collaboratively (UNESCO, 2022). It encompasses practices such as making research outputs open (e.g.,
84 open access, open data, and open source), verifiable, and reproducible. This openness provides many
85 additional benefits, for instance making it easier to publish and communicate scientific knowledge,
86 expedite the scientific process by saving time for re-inventing methods, receive constructive feedback
87 from the scientific community, and promote collaborative, cross-disciplinary, and inclusive research
88 practices. Moreover, open data can help identify systematic data misuse (i.e., a potentially adverse use
89 that was not originally intended), particularly when technical data issues arise (e.g., Flaherty et al.,
90 2022). Open science is further guided by the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016), ensuring
91 **F**indability, **A**ccessibility, **I**nteroperability, and **R**euse of digital assets. Moreover, open access licenses
92 (see Table 1) ensure an unrestricted use of data, models, or other outputs while appropriately crediting
93 the creator. By complying with these standards and principles, cross-disciplinary efforts are possible
94 and long-term access can be ensured (COAR et al., 2021).

95 Dynamic (seismic) risk assessment requires linking information from different assets and different
96 phases of the disaster cycle, therefore significantly benefitting from an open approach. The European
97 Plate Observing System ([EPOS](#)), partner of the RISE project, exemplarily positioned itself to advance
98 the open and FAIR data transfer between institutions and multiple disciplines within solid-earth sciences
99 (Bailo et al., 2022; Marti et al., 2022). For instance, the *EPOS Thematic Core Service for Seismology*
100 (Haslinger et al., 2022) enables homogenized monitoring efforts and collaboration based on seismic
101 waveform data ([ORFEUS](#)), rapid earthquake information ([EMSC](#)), and expertise in seismic hazard and
102 risk assessments ([EFEHR](#)); thus connecting the different assets along the disaster cycle. Also in RISE,
103 some open science assets have been created, such as the pyCSEP toolkit and so-called reproducibility
104 packages (Savran et al., 2022; Bayona et al., 2022; Khawaja et al., 2023). These packages permit readers
105 and users to fully reproduce research outcomes without additional effort following the concept of open
106 science, thereby setting an example for making the fundamental assets of dynamic (seismic) risk
107 assessment available. For the 2023 Türkiye–Syria earthquake sequence, various initiatives (e.g., EERI,
108 2023; GDACS, 2023; GSNL, 2023) collected open data and reports to facilitate scientific investigation,
109 understanding, and dynamic risk reduction strategies.

110 To date, several challenges restrict the dissemination and development of open science. Here we
111 emphasize three of them: (i) Open science is not yet fully recognized as a part of science education,
112 therefore authorities (e.g., universities, science ministries, research centers, funders) responsible for
113 overseeing science should emphasize more on open science; (ii) The tools and technologies being used
114 for open science are either unfamiliar or unavailable to many scientists, thereby keeping them away
115 from doing open science. Training and open tools for the collaborative development of code, data, and
116 methods should be provided to researchers early in their careers, i.e. during their PhD or even before;
117 (iii) Open science demands time, which is not yet considered in the researchers' evaluation process.
118 Efforts for open science should be rewarded during the evaluation process of a researcher, for example
119 through qualitative assessments (e.g., Hicks et al., 2015; see also [DORA](#), [Leiden Manifesto](#), [CoARA](#)).

120 **2.2 *Transdisciplinarity***

121 Addressing current societal challenges requires not only integrating knowledge from different
122 scientific disciplines (interdisciplinary), but also considering values, knowledge, and expertise from
123 stakeholders of the society (transdisciplinarity; Vienni Baptista et al., 2020). This transdisciplinary
124 approach acknowledges the societal and scientific complexity of a problem (Hirsch Hadorn et al., 2008),
125 co-creates knowledge and practices (Pohl et al., 2021), tailors general scientific concepts to the local
126 context (Stablein et al., 2022), and develops user-centered assets to contribute to disaster risk reduction
127 (Dallo, 2022; Raška, 2022). Fostering transdisciplinarity is indispensable because we, as scientists, have
128 a societal responsibility (Di Capua & Peppoloni, 2021) since our scientific outputs can have a direct or
129 indirect impact on people's lives (Marti et al., 2022).

130 Transdisciplinary efforts to assess risk perception and awareness across communities and
131 stakeholders are essential for disaster risk reduction (UNDRR, 2022a). The dynamic seismic risk
132 framework develops products for different stakeholders who actively participate in all phases of the
133 disaster cycle. In RISE, different stakeholders, including scientific experts from different disciplines,
134 professional stakeholders, communication experts, and the general public, were involved in focus
135 groups, interviews, and surveys to collect their feedback and develop communication guidelines (Fallou
136 et al., 2022). It became apparent that a key factor in improving risk mitigation strategies is strengthening
137 the relationship between scientists and stakeholders to better understand societies' needs and concerns,
138 as well as to build trust in authoritative earthquake information.

139 Transdisciplinarity is not yet fully practiced by actors involved in disaster risk reduction activities,
140 and is not included in current discipline-specific academic education programs despite the desire of early
141 career scientists (Bridle et al., 2013; Supplement 3). One of the main challenges is the difficulty of
142 engaging civil society, particularly minority groups, and assessing their knowledge, perception, and
143 preparedness. This engagement requires a structured and sometimes long process by building trust
144 between scientists and stakeholders (UNDRR, 2022b). Developing effective risk-related
145 communication is also challenged by potential misinformation, disinformation, and/or
146 misunderstandings among the wide range of actors involved, for which targeted information is defined

147 depending on their role and needs. This has been again observed in the 2023 Türkiye–Syria earthquake
148 sequence (e.g., Panjwani, 2023). Thus, communication experts must be aware of these dynamics and
149 continue to provide useful, understandable, and evidence-based recommendations to combat earthquake
150 misinformation (Dallo et al., 2022), help design and implement strategies for efficiently communicating
151 earthquake early warnings and earthquake forecasts (Dryhurst et al., 2021; Freeman et al., 2023), train
152 others to improve their communication skills, and foster multi-hazard communication among different
153 stakeholders (Dallo, 2022).

154 **2.3 Ethics**

155 Ethics is relevant to data collection and data-driven decision-making – so it must be consciously
156 considered by researchers. In general, experts differentiate between internal and external (research)
157 ethics (ALLEA, 2013). Internal ethics refer to good research practices such as complying with GDPR
158 and FAIR data principles, reflecting on conflicts of interest or embracing the duty to produce open
159 science (Di Capua & Peppoloni, 2021; Wilkinson et al., 2016). External research ethics refer to the
160 relations between science and society such as the potential misuse, the responsibility towards society,
161 or legal consequences (e.g., trial in L’Aquila in 2009) (ALLEA, 2013). These relations have a long
162 history, starting with defined ethical standards after World War II (Evers, 2001). Even though
163 international, European, and national ethical guidelines have been established (e.g., AGU, 2017), their
164 practical implementation is still in its early stages (Di Capua and Peppoloni, 2021).

165 An open approach makes us scientists responsible for potential misuse of data and models involved
166 in dynamic seismic risk. For instance, a false earthquake early warning alert could cause widespread
167 panic and significant financial losses. Ethics also matters when communicating certain information; in
168 the workshop we discussed whether we can simply release probabilistic earthquake forecasts to the
169 public (and if yes, how?). Although those probabilities are available to the scientific community, not
170 every scientist may advocate their public release for ethical reasons (e.g., potential misinterpretation,
171 unintended panic, missing knowledge on translating the probabilities into mitigation actions) – yet, our
172 internal majority voted for an unconditional public release, arguing that some information is more useful
173 for (personal) decision-making than no information.

174 But ethically, who decides what is actually considered right or wrong? We identified three possible
175 categories: (i) ‘agreed upon’, where the necessary action to undertake is obvious, such as doing open
176 science, involving more reviewers in the review process to reduce bias, or improving education; (ii)
177 ‘subjective’, where a consensus is needed (such as publicly releasing forecasts), which can be obtained
178 via voting (democratic) or providing and discussing arguments; and (iii) ‘I do not care’, where ethical
179 implications are ignored or considered irrelevant. For the second category, which is the most difficult
180 one, one may not find a consensus easily and need to wait for more information or better arguments.
181 Interestingly, a democratic approach to consensus building may in itself be considered unethical because
182 minorities are not adequately represented. Therefore, evaluating ethical implications in practical

183 applications of research results is not trivial – potential unethical situations must be carefully considered
 184 and reflected upon.

185 3 So, what can we do now?

186 On all levels – individually, lab-specific, institutionally, nationally, and internationally – more
 187 efforts are needed to foster open science, jointly discuss the ethical implications of our research, and
 188 shift from discipline-specific or interdisciplinary research to transdisciplinary research.
 189 Transdisciplinarity, in particular, is not sufficiently rewarded and encouraged within the academic sector
 190 (Müller & Kalterbrunner, 2019), and all three subjects presented here are only partially addressed during
 191 academic training and career development.

192 In Table 1 we provide some practical guidelines and general suggestions on how to better address
 193 these three subjects. We advocate that research institutes and supervisors integrate them in their training
 194 programs for early career scientists, go beyond purely discipline-oriented training, motivate other
 195 scientists to proactively reflect on and consider these subjects in their projects, and bring them up in
 196 discussions with colleagues (from other disciplines) or outside academia. We further suggest that
 197 researchers’ activities also need to be evaluated based on their contributions in terms of
 198 transdisciplinarity, openness, and ethical compliance to promote excellence and fairness. Finally, on an
 199 university, institutional, or project level, we argue that sessions with practical guidelines are needed to
 200 ensure that current and future research excellence considers the three subjects. Only then can we, as
 201 scientists, address current societal challenges and ultimately contribute to increasing societies’ resilience
 202 to disasters.

203
 204 *Table 1: A selection of practical guidelines for each of the three subjects (middle column) and general suggestions to*
 205 *proactively address them (right column). The last row refers to all three subjects.*

The subjects	Practical guidelines	General suggestions
Open Science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – FAIR Principles – OpenAire Open Science Guides – Open Science Training in TRIPLE (Provost et al., 2023) – Ten rules for implementing open and reproducible research practices (Heise et al., 2023) – Open Data Commons Licenses – Creative Commons Licenses – Open Source Initiative – Licenses Overview – EC’s Joinup Software License Assistant – European Commission: Open Science 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Provide training and use open tools for a collaborative development of code, data, and methods. – Incentives to focus on open science, e.g., publishing software packages should be acknowledged in performance evaluations (Journal of Open Source Software, Merow et al., 2023). – Incentives for qualitative evaluations of researcher output, e.g., DORA, Leiden Manifesto, CoARA.
Transdisciplinarity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – td-net toolbox – What is transdisciplinary research? – Ten steps to make your research more relevant – EU action catalogue – Participatory methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Professors should actively share their knowledge about stakeholders’ decision-making processes with their junior scientists, e.g., by dedicated seminars. – Training activities (e.g., workshops) where researchers can directly apply

- [Communication Guide: How to fight misinformation about earthquakes?](#) (Dallo et al., 2022)
 - transdisciplinarity methods, which they can use for their research.
 - Real-world laboratories to facilitate the co-production between scientists and stakeholders (Pärli et al., 2022).
 - Promote more inter- and transdisciplinary interactions (Bridle et al. 2013).
- Ethics
- [Ethics Education in Science](#)
 - [Artificial Intelligence & Ethics](#)
 - [Code of Conduct for Scientific Integrity](#)
 - [What is Ethics in Research](#)
 - [International Association for Promoting Geoethics](#)
 -
 - Claim support for assessing ethical implications of research activities (e.g., ethical review specialists).
 - Improve review mechanisms to avoid bias and subjectivity.
 - Build consensus by considering diverse perspectives.
 - Foster practices and approaches for fieldwork (Ryan-Davis & Scalice, 2022).
- All three subjects
- [The Turing Way](#): Practical handbook with focus on reproducible, collaborative, and ethical research
 - [Best practices for transparent, reproducible, and ethical research](#) (Hoces De La Guardia et al., 2019)
 - Training courses for early career scientists, seniors, supervisors, etc. (at the institutes) (Nature, 2023).
 - Project workshops discussing these subjects in the light of the overall project theme or subtasks (as we did, see Supplement S1).
 - Build reward mechanisms for research that adopts transdisciplinarity, comply with open access principles, and/or covers ethical aspects.
 - Supervisors should be role models (Haven et al., 2022).
 - Engage in knowledge transfer and dissemination activities to the society.

206

207 Data and Resources

208 The outputs of the RISE ECS Workshop are available in the Supplement:
 209 <https://polybox.ethz.ch/index.php/s/pqadhYVzcxONFPb> (last accessed March 2023)

210 **[Remark:** If the manuscript will be accepted, we will upload the Supplement to the ETH Research
 211 Collection and add here the DOI].

212 Declaration of Competing Interests

213 The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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229

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